

Synthesis and pharmacological evaluation of 2-(3',5'-dichlorobenzo[b]thiophen-2'-yl)-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles and 2-arylsulfonylhydrazinocarbonyl-3,5-dichlorobenzo[b]thiophenes

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2-(3',5'-Dichlorobenzo[b]thiophen-2'-yl)-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (**2a-l**) were obtained from the 2-hydrazino carbonyl-3,5-dichlorobenzo[b]thiophene (**1**) by the reaction with different arylsulfonyl chlorides afforded the corresponding 2-arylsulfonylhydrazinocarbonyl-3,5-dichlorobenzo[b]thiophenes (**3a-l**). The structures of newly synthesized compounds were established on the basis of elemental analysis, IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectral data. The pharmacological evaluations were performed for their antitubercular and antimicrobial activities.

In continuation of our earlier work¹ we report here synthesis of some 1,3,4-oxadiazoles (**2a-l**) and sulfonamides (**3a-l**) and their pharmacological evaluations. Condensation of 2-hydrazinocarbonyl-3,5-dichlorobenzo[b]thiophene (**1**) with different aromatic acids in presence of POCl₃ gave the compounds 2-(3',5'-dichlorobenzo[b]thiophene-2'-yl)-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (**2a-l**). Reaction of (**1**) with different arylsulfonyl chloride², yielded 2-arylsulfonylhydrazinocarbonyl-3,5-dichlorobenzo[b]thiophenes (**3a-l**).

The structures of the synthesized compounds were assigned on the basis of elemental analyses, IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectral data. The compounds were screened for their antitubercular and antimicrobial activities.

The antitubercular evaluation of the compounds was carried out at Tuberculosis Antimicrobial Acquisition Coordinating Facility (TAACF), USA. Primary screening of the compounds for antitubercular activity has been conducted at 6.25 µg/ml against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H₃₇Rv in BACTEC 12B medium using the ALAMAR radiometric system. The antimicrobial activity data were compared with standard drug Rifampin at 0.25 µg/ml concentration which showed 98% inhibition.

The activity was determined using cup-plate agar diffusion method³ by measuring the inhibition zone in mm. All the compounds were screened *in vitro* for their antimicrobial activity against a variety of microbial strains such as *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Bacillus magaterium*, *Staphylococcus* and fungi stains as *Aspergillus niger*. Known antibiotics like benzyl penicillin,

amoxicillin, ciprofloxacin, erythromycin and griseofulvin showed highest activity (15–28 mm) against these organisms. The data of compounds that exhibited highest activity. It could be observed that compounds **2d** (18), **3c** (30), **3d** (20), **3f** (30), **3g** (19), **3h** (25) were active against *E. coli*. Compounds **2e** (20), **2f** (22), **2g** (22), **2l** (25), **3c** (25), **3f**

R

2a C₆H₅-
2b 2-OCOCH₃-C₆H₄-
2c 3-Cl-CH=CH-C₆H₄-
2d 4-Cl-C₆H₄-
2e 2,4-(OH)₂-C₆H₃-
2f -CH₂-NH-CO-C₆H₅
2g 2-OH-C₆H₄-
2h 2-OH-C₁₀H₆-
2i 4-OH-C₆H₄-
2j 3-CH₃-C₆H₄-
2k 4-CH₃-C₆H₄-
2l 3-OC₆H₅-CH=CH-C₆H₄-

R'

3a 4-NHCOCH₃-C₆H₄-
3b 3-COOH-C₆H₄-
3c 2-Br-5-COOH-C₆H₃-
3d 4-Br-C₆H₄-
3e 3-COOH-4-OH-C₆H₃-
3f 2-Cl-5-COOH-C₆H₃-
3g 4-Cl-C₆H₄-
3h 2-CH=CH-COOH-C₆H₄-
3i 2-OCH₃-5-COOH-C₆H₃-
3j 2-CH₃-5-NHCOCH₃-C₆H₃-
3k 2-CH₃-5-COOH-C₆H₃-
3l 4-CH₂-C₆H₄-

(25) were active against *P. aeruginosa*. Compounds **2e** (25), **2f** (28), **2h** (25), **3d** (28), **3f** (22), **3i** (2) were active against *B. mega*. Compounds **2a** (22), **2h** (20), **2j** (20), **3b** (20), **3g** (21), **3l** (20) were active against *S. aureus*. Compounds **2e** (22), **2f** (25), **2g** (23), **2i** (26), **2j** (28), **3g** (22), **3i** (26) displayed maximum activity against *A. niger*.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) (cm^{-1}) were recorded on Shimadzu-8400 FTIR spectrophotometer and ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker spectrometer (300 MHz) using TMS as an internal standard (chemical shift in δ). The purity of the compounds were checked on TLC. All the synthesized compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N analysis.

Preparation of 2-(3',5'-dichlorobenzo[b]thiophen-2'-yl)-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (2k) :

A mixture of 2-hydrazinocarbonyl-3,5-dichlorobenzo[b]thiophene (2.61 g, 0.01 M) and *p*-toluic acid (0.01 M) in POCl_3 (5 ml) were refluxed for 5–6 h. The content was cooled and poured on crushed ice. It was neutralized with sodium bicarbonate solution. Resulting solid was filtered, dried and crystallized from dioxane. **2k** : (52%), m.p. 205° (Found : C, 56.51; H, 2.77; N, 7.75. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}_2\text{Cl}_2$ requires : C, 56.84; H, 2.74; N, 7.71%); IR (KBr) 1577 (C=N), 1078 (C–O–C), 781 (C–Cl), 617 (C–S–C) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3 + $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ 7.34–8.0 (7H, m, Ar-H), 2.47 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$); m/z 360.

Similarly other compounds : **2a**, m.p. 110°; **b**, >300°; **c**, 110°; **d**, 160°; **e**, 260°; **f**, 115°; **g**, 120°; **h**, 160°; **i**, >300°; **j**, 170°; **k**, 205°; **l**, 120°; (yields 47–57%) were prepared.

Preparation of 2-arylsulfonylhydrazinocarbonyl-3,5-dichlorobenzo[b]thiophenes (3l) :

A mixture of *p*-tolyl sulphonyl chloride (1.90 g, 0.01 M) and 2-hydrazinocarbonyl-3,5-dichlorobenzo[b]thiophene (2.61 g, 0.01 M) was refluxed in dry pyridine for 5 h. The resulting mixture was poured on crushed ice and product was isolated. It was crystallized from ethanol. **3l** : (58%), m.p. 200° (Found : C, 46.26; H, 2.89; N, 6.75. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{S}_2\text{Cl}_2$ requires : C, 44.20; H, 2.88; N, 6.73%); IR (KBr) 3197 (N–H. sec. amine), 169 (C=O, sec. amide), 1309 (S=O), 783 (C–Cl), 621 (C–S–C) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3 + $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ 8.89 (1H, s, $-\text{NH}$), 7.08–7.82 (7H, m, Ar-H), 2.31 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$); m/z 416.

Similarly other compounds : **3a**, m.p. 190°; **b**, 180°; **c**, 240°; **d**, 195°; **e**, 205°; **f**, 200°; **g**, 170°; **h**, 270°; **i**, 195°; **j**, 240°; **k**, 185°; **l**, 200°; (yields 52–58%) were prepared.

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